

New Small Wheel Radiation and Magnetic Field Environment

Ryan Edgar,

Jon Ameel, Dan Amidei, Karishma Sekhon Edgar, Liang Guan

University of Michigan, Ann Arbor

450 Church St, Ann Arbor, MI 48109, United States

November 19, 2015

This document is intended to briefly summarize the expected radiation and magnetic field environment of the ATLAS New Small Wheel (NSW) and to specify required tolerances for on-detector electronics, including safety factors.

Revised 17-Aug-2015: This revision includes several changes: simulation updates include new JD shielding; revised methodology for extracting simulated radiation levels; revised safety factors; and prescriptive radiation tolerance criteria for each on-detector board.

Revised 30-Oct-2015: This revision corrects several small typographical errors and adjusts the B -field criteria and safety factors for the rack locations.

Revised 19-Nov-2015: The stated design luminosity has been adjusted from 5000 fb^{-1} to 3000 fb^{-1} , with corresponding adjustments to the stated radiation loads.

1 Radiation Load

The radiation load is described by three quantities: Total Ionizing Dose (TID), measured in Grays (Gy); Non-Ionizing Energy Loss (NIEL), measured in terms of the equivalent fluence of 1 MeV neutrons; and the fluence of potentially single-event-inducing particles (SEE), for which the fluence of hadrons above 20 MeV is used as a proxy. These effects are quantified using simulated radiation levels (SRL) extracted from FLUKA simulations developed by the ATLAS simulation group.

The underlying simulations are produced at a center-of-mass energy of $\sqrt{\hat{s}} = 14 \text{ TeV}$ and instantaneous luminosity of $\mathcal{L} = 1 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$. The geometry includes the Run III JD shielding in place of the prior JD configuration, as well as the Run II aluminum beam pipe. It does not include the mechanical details of the NSW, instead assuming a uniform, average material density in the NSW volume. The results of the simulation are then scaled to an expected lifetime of 10 yr at $3 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ (i.e. 3000 fb^{-1}).

New Small Wheel Simulated Radiation Loads and Magnetic Fields

		Inner Rim ($R = 1$ m)	Outer Rim ($R = 5$ m)
TID	(γ)	460 Gy	16 Gy
NIEL	(fast neutrons)	2.3×10^{13} n/cm ²	7.3×10^{11} n/cm ²
SEE ¹	(protons)	4.2×10^{12} p/cm ²	1.3×10^{11} p/cm ²
B field		≤ 1 kG	5 kG

¹ Simulated number of hadrons with $E > 20$ MeV

Table 1: Simulated radiation loads for the NSW after 10 years at an LHC luminosity of $\mathcal{L} = 5 \times 10^{34}$ cm⁻² s⁻¹. Safety factors are **not** included. Magnetic field levels are also shown.

Because this simulation does not include the mechanical details of the NSW, and because the radiation load depends strongly on the radial position and little or not at all on z , we extract the SRLs by averaging over the z extent of the NSW to produce the SRLs as a function of radius. These are shown in terms of the yearly dose at $\mathcal{L} = 3 \times 10^{34}$ cm⁻² s⁻¹ in Figures 1, 2 and 3 (TID, NIEL, and SEE, respectively). Radiation loads at the extreme inner and extreme outer radii of the NSW are summarized in Table 1; the inner radius of the detector is subject to some $20 - 30\times$ the radiation load of the outer radius.

2 Safety Factors for Electronics

The ATLAS Policy on Radiation-Tolerant Electronics [1] specifies safety factors that must be applied to the simulated radiation loads to determine the radiation tolerance criteria (RTC) for on-detector electronics:

$$RTC = SRL \times SF_{\text{sim}} \times SF_{\text{ldr}} \times SF_{\text{batch}} \quad (1)$$

The safety factors account for simulation uncertainties (SF_{sim}), low-dose-rate effects (SF_{ldr}), and lot-to-lot variation (SF_{batch}), respectively. In general, they depend on the technology of the device in question (COTS vs. radiation-hard ASIC), lot control, and testing methodology. The safety factors are summarized in Table 2. Reference [1] should be consulted for full details, however, a few common cases are summarized below:

1. Qualification of radiation-hard ASICs, no control for dose-rate effects.

$$SF(\text{tid}) = 1.5 \times 1.5 \times 1.0 = 2.25$$

$$SF(\text{niel}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 2.0$$

$$SF(\text{see}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 2.0$$

Radiation safety factors for New Small Wheel electronics.

Safety Factor	Type	Value	Notes
SF_{sim}	TID	1.5	Updated from [1] as per [2]
	NIEL	2.0	Updated from [1] as per [2]
	SEE	2.0	Updated from [1] as per [2]
SF_{ldr}	TID	5.0	COTS, no control for low-dose-rate effects.
	TID	1.5	ASIC, no control for low-dose-rate effects.
	TID	1.0	COTS/ASIC, accelerated aging or low-rate tests.
	NIEL	1.0	
	SEE	1.0	
SF_{lot}	all	4.0	Unknown COTS batches.
	all	2.0	Preselection; homogenous COTS or ASIC batches.
	all	1.0	Qualification; homogenous COTS or ASIC batches.

Table 2: Safety factors for on-detector electronics, as according to [1, 2], along with details on the applicable conditions.

2. Qualification of radiation-hard ASICs, accelerated aging or low-rate TID testing.

$$SF(\text{tid}) = 1.5 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 1.5$$

$$SF(\text{niel}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 2.0$$

$$SF(\text{see}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 2.0$$

3. Unknown COTS batches, no control for dose-rate effects.

$$SF(\text{tid}) = 1.5 \times 5.0 \times 4.0 = 30.0$$

$$SF(\text{niel}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 4.0 = 8.0$$

$$SF(\text{see}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 4.0 = 8.0$$

4. Preselection of COTS parts that will be qualified in homogenous batches, accelerated aging or low-rate TID testing.

$$SF(\text{tid}) = 1.5 \times 1.0 \times 2.0 = 3.0$$

$$SF(\text{niel}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 2.0 = 4.0$$

$$SF(\text{see}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 2.0 = 4.0$$

5. Qualification of COTS parts from homogenous batches.

$$SF(\text{tid}) = 1.5 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 1.5$$

$$SF(\text{niel}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 2.0$$

$$SF(\text{see}) = 2.0 \times 1.0 \times 1.0 = 2.0$$

3 Magnetic Field

The New Small Wheel is within the fringing fields of the toroidal bending magnets. These are very well-understood from particle tracking studies. In the NSW volume, the field ranges from negligible (inner radius) to over 5 kG (large sector corners). The majority of the NSW is subject to a field of less than 3 kG.

The magnetic fields in the large sector with the greatest field are shown in Figure 4. Similarly, the small sector with greatest field is shown in Figure 5. Strong radial field components are present at large radii, but diminish rapidly as the beamline is approached. The intermediate regions are subject to more moderate fields in the ϕ - and z -directions, while the innermost region of the NSW has only small fields.

4 Requirements for On-Detector Electronics

For the purpose of specifying radiation-tolerance criteria for the New Small Wheel, the electronics have been divided into four categories by location, detailed below. The resulting radiation tolerance requirements are enumerated in Table 3.

Note that in all cases the low-dose-rate safety factor SF_{ldr} for on-detector electronics is set to 1.0. This is predicated on the assumption that the TID testing is either accompanied by accelerated aging tests as per Ref. [1], or that the exposures are conducted under sufficiently long-term, low-rate conditions that any aging effects can be expected to manifest. If this is not the case, this safety factor should be set to $SF_{\text{ldr}} = 1.5$ (front-end boards, L1DDC, and ADDC), or $SF_{\text{ldr}} = 5.0$ (rim electronics).

The electronics are categorized as follows:

- **Front-end electronics.** The locations of the front-end boards include the most severe radiation loads in the NSW region. However, the front-end boards are constructed around radiation-hard ASICs, allowing the use of reduced safety factors. It is assumed that if the front-end boards require any non-passive COTS components, those components will be qualified separately.
- **Peripheral boards.** The L1DDC and ADDC are likewise constructed around radiation-hard ASICs, and are therefore assigned the same safety factors as the front-end boards. However, the worst-case radiation levels are much lower due to the greater distance from the beamline.

- **Rim electronics.** The electronics on the NSW rim experience the lowest radiation load of the on-detector electronics. These boards will contain numerous commercial components, and so are assigned the appropriate larger safety factors.
- **Racks.** The racks in the ATLAS cavern that will be used for the New Small Wheel are taken to be located at $(r, z) = (14 \text{ m}, \pm 11 \text{ m})$ with respect to the IP. The radiation load and magnetic field at this location are quite moderate. Unfortunately, the radiation maps do not extend this far from the beam line. The numerical values are evaluated at the closest available location, which is the point $(r, z) = (12 \text{ m}, 11 \text{ m})$.

References

- [1] *ATLAS Policy on Radiation Tolerant Electronics*, http://atlas.web.cern.ch/Atlas/GROUPS/FRONTEND/WWW/RAD/RadWebPage/ATLASPolicy/APRTE_rev2_250800.pdf
- [2] Lanni, F. *et. al. Report of the Radiation Estimate Task-Force*, https://edms.cern.ch/edmsui/file/1293497/1/FL_RETF_Report.pdf

New Small Wheel Environmental Tolerance Requirements

		SRL	SF_{sim}	SF_{ldr}	SF_{batch}	Requirement
Front-End Electronics (MMFE, Strip FE, Pad FE; $r = 1$ m)						
TID	(Gy)	460	1.5	1.0	1.0	690
NIEL	(n/cm ²)	2.3×10^{13}	2.0	1.0	1.0	4.6×10^{13}
SEE ⁽¹⁾	(p/cm ²)	4.2×10^{12}	2.0	1.0	1.0	8.4×10^{12}
B field	(G)	4.0×10^3				4.0×10^3
Peripheral Boards (ADDC, L1DDC; $r = 2.8$ m)						
TID	(Gy)	52	1.5	1.0	1.0	78
NIEL	(n/cm ²)	2.4×10^{12}	2.0	1.0	1.0	4.8×10^{12}
SEE ⁽¹⁾	(p/cm ²)	4.3×10^{11}	2.0	1.0	1.0	8.6×10^{12}
B field	(G)	4.0×10^3				4.0×10^3
Rim Electronics (Router, Pad Trigger, LV Intermediate Conversion Stage; $r = 5$ m)						
TID	(Gy)	16	1.5	1.0	4.0	96
NIEL	(n/cm ²)	7.3×10^{11}	2.0	1.0	4.0	5.8×10^{12}
SEE ⁽¹⁾	(p/cm ²)	1.3×10^{11}	2.0	1.0	4.0	1.0×10^{12}
B field	(G)	6.0×10^3				6.0×10^3
Racks ⁽²⁾ ($r = 14$ m, $z = 11$ m)						
TID	(Gy)	4.2	1.5	5.0	4.0	130
NIEL	(n/cm ²)	7.2×10^{10}	2.0	1.0	4.0	5.8×10^{11}
SEE ⁽¹⁾	(p/cm ²)	1.8×10^{10}	2.0	1.0	4.0	1.4×10^{11}
B field	(G)	200	5.0			1.0×10^3

⁽¹⁾ Simulated number of hadrons with $E > 20$ MeV

⁽²⁾ Evaluated using $r = 12$ m, the largest radius available in the radiation maps.

Table 3: The simulated magnetic field and radiation load for the New Small Wheel for various equipment. The table also includes the designated safety factors and resulting radiation tolerance requirements. Values are shown to two significant figures.

Figure 1: The simulated TID dose for the NSW (Gy/10yr). The values are scaled to an LHC luminosity of $\mathcal{L} = 3 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}$

Figure 2: The simulated NIEL dose for the NSW (n/cm²–10yr) 1 MeV-equivalent). The values are scaled to an LHC luminosity of $\mathcal{L} = 3 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}$.

Figure 3: The simulated fluence of hadrons having $E > 20$ MeV in the NSW ($\text{p}/\text{cm}^2/10\text{yr}$). The values are scaled to an LHC luminosity of $\mathcal{L} = 3 \times 10^{34} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}$

Figure 4: The magnetic field in the large sectors of the New Small Wheel closest to the toroidal bending magnetics. The plots are produced at $z = 7900$ mm from the IP. Shown are the total field ((a)) and its components in the ϕ direction ((b)), the radial direction ((c)), and the z direction ((d)). Note that the individual plots have somewhat different scales.

Figure 5: The magnetic field in the small sectors of the New Small Wheel closest to the toroidal bending magnetics. The plots are produced at $z = 7435$ mm from the IP. Shown are the total field ((a)) and its components in the ϕ direction ((b)), the radial direction ((c)), and the z direction ((d)). Note that the individual plots have somewhat different scales.